

NEW COMPOUNDS OF GALLIUM. PART V. GALLIUM ALIZARIN LAKES,
GALLIUM SALTS OF GEOMETRICALLY AND OPTICALLY ISOMERIC
ACIDS AND DOUBLE SULPHATES WITH ETHYLENE- AND
PROPYLENEDIAMINE SULPHATES.

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Gallium alizarate and gallium-calcium alizarate have been obtained. These 'lakes' are red in colour, the gallium lake being as scarlet as the corresponding aluminium compound and the calcium-gallium lake dull red in colour. These can be fastened on cotton, woolen and silk fabrics. Other salts prepared are *d*- and *l*-gallium camphor sulphates and their optical rotations have been measured. Ethylene- and propylenediammonium gallium sulphates have also been prepared.

In the present paper more new compounds of gallium are described. Two gallium lakes with alizarin have been prepared. One is gallium alizarate, the other is calcium-gallium alizarate. The gallium lake is obtained as a scarlet precipitate and has the composition Ga (C₁₄H₁₇O₄)₂ like the corresponding aluminium and trivalent iron and chromium alizarates (Mahlau, *Ber.*, 1913, 46, 443). It dissolves readily in ammonia and other alkalis and should contain one hydroxyl group. The compound may be represented as

If the solution of gallium alizarate in ammonia is treated with an equivalent quantity of calcium chloride the remaining hydroxylic hydrogen is replaced by the bivalent metal and calcium-gallium alizarate is obtained as a red precipitate. The compound has the composition Ga₂Ca₂(C₁₄H₁₆O₄)₂ and may be represented as

This compound is analogous to the corresponding aluminium, iron and chromium lakes containing calcium obtained by Mahlau (*loc. cit.*). The two compounds are stable substances and may be precipitated as red dyes on cotton, woolen and silk fabrics in the same manner as aluminium alizarates are used as a dye, the gallium lake being as scarlet as the aluminium lake. The red dye obtained as calcium-gallium alizarate has a less scarlet shade than the gallium alizarate.

In our attempts to prepare gallium salts of geometrically and optically isomeric acids, it has been possible to prepare a gallium salt of maleic acid by dissolving freshly prepared gallium hydroxide in maleic acid but gallium fumarate could not be obtained in a similar manner. Both *d*- and *l*-camphorsulphonic acids also dissolved freshly prepared gallium hydroxide and gave dextro rotatory and laevo rotatory camphorsulphonates respectively. The optical rotations of these compounds have been measured in aqueous solutions. Other compounds described are the double salts of gallium sulphate with ethylenediamine and propylenediamine sulphates.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Gallium Alizarate.—A concentrated aqueous solution of potassium alizarate was prepared. When it was added to an aqueous solution of gallium nitrate or sulphate, a scarlet precipitate of gallium alizarate was at once formed. It was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and then dried in air. [Found : C, 63.24 ; H, 2.66 ; Ga, 8.21. (C₁₄H₁₇O₄)₂Ga requires C, 64.04 ; H, 2.7 ; Ga, 8.89 per cent].

It is insoluble in water but soluble in alcohol. It dissolves readily in ammonia. Gallium alizarate is a fast lake for cotton fibres. The fibre is first dipped into a solution of alizarin in caustic soda or caustic potash and afterwards into an aqueous solution of a gallium salt. The fibre is then dyed deep red which cannot be washed out by soaping. Fibres of wool and silk can also be dyed using gallium alizarate as a lake.

Calcium-gallium Alizarate.—Gallium alizarate (2 g.) was dissolved in ammonia when a violet solution was obtained. Calcium chloride (0.5 g.) was also dissolved in water. The two solutions were then mixed. At once a dull red precipitate appeared. The precipitate was allowed to settle and then filtered. After washing thoroughly with water it was dried in air. [Found: C, 59.03; H, 2.42; Ga, 8.01; Ca, 7.56. $(C_{14}H_8O_4)_2Ga_2Ca_2$ requires C, 59.77; H, 2.13; Ga, 8.29; Ca, 7.11 per cent]. It is insoluble in water and ammonia. Calcium-gallium alizarate is a fast lake for cotton, wool and silk.

Gallium Maleate.—Excess of freshly prepared gallium hydroxide was treated with an aqueous solution of maleic acid when a portion of it dissolved. The undissolved hydroxide was filtered off and the filtrate evaporated in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid. It could also be evaporated on a water-bath. The solid obtained was crystallised from water and analysed after drying in air for two days. [Found: C, 27.85; H, 2.16; Ga, 27.32. $(C_4H_2O_4)_2Ga_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ requires C, 27.8; H, 1.93; Ga, 27.03 per cent]. Gallium maleate is a white crystalline substance. It is soluble in water and is not decomposed by boiling with water for a short time.

Gallium dextroCamphorsulphonate.—It was prepared by dissolving gallium hydroxide in an aqueous solution of *d*-camphorsulphonic acid and evaporating the solution obtained in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid. It was purified by crystallisation from water and analysed after drying between folds of filter papers. [Found: S, 11.24; Ga, 8.23. $(C_{10}H_{16}SO_4)_2Ga \cdot 3H_2O$ require S, 11.75; Ga, 8.57 per cent]. 5% Solution gave $[\alpha]_D^{25} = 18.6$; $[M] = +152$. The camphorsulphonate is very soluble in water. It is also soluble in alcohol.

Gallium laevoCamphorsulphonate.—It was obtained as a crystalline solid like the dextro compound by using freshly prepared gallium hydroxide and *l*-camphorsulphonic acid. [Found: S, 11.16; Ga, 8.49. $(C_{10}H_{16}SO_4)_2Ga \cdot 3H_2O$ requires S, 11.75; Ga, 8.57 per cent]. It is similar in properties to the *dextro* compound except that it is *laevorotatory* in solution. 5% Aqueous solution gave $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -19$. $[M] = -155$.

Ethylenediammonium Gallium Sulphate.—Saturated aqueous solutions of ethylenediamine sulphate and gallium sulphate taken in equimolecular proportions were mixed. The double sulphate was then precipitated by the addition of alcohol and ether to the mixed solution. It was then crystallised from water and obtained in the form of colourless plates. [Found: N, 3.52; Ga, 17.91; SO_4 , 48.37. $Ga_2(SO_4)_3 \cdot C_2H_4(NH_2)_2SO_4 \cdot 12H_2O$ requires N, 3.49; Ga, 17.46; SO_4 , 47.88. per cent]. It is soluble in water but insoluble in alcohol. On keeping, it did not change and remained completely soluble in water.

Propylenediammonium Gallium Sulphate.—It was obtained as the ethylenediamine compound by mixing together saturated aqueous solutions of a molecule of propylenediamine sulphate and a molecule of gallium sulphate and precipitating by means of alcohol and ether. [Found: N, 3.69; Ga, 17.81; SO_4 , 46.5. $Ga_2(SO_4)_3 \cdot C_3H_7(NH_2)_2SO_4 \cdot 12H_2O$ requires N, 3.43; Ga, 17.16; SO_4 , 47.06 per cent]. In crystalline form and properties it is similar to the corresponding ethylene diammonium compound.